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FIRRE activation during metastasis to the lungs.

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We describe here activation of the DXZ4 locus Xist regulatory non-coding RNA *FIRRE* in metastasis to the lungs in humans with breast cancer.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the lungs to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the lung metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer: a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: FIRRE.

Results

Figure 1: FIRRE is differentially expressed in lung metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

I. Lung metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=6 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

n=2 lung metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
286467	2.96E-02	1.082	-2.175006	-2.3538455	125.6	FIRRE	3224/22997	86.0

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in lung metastases of humans with breast cancer (9), we discovered differential expression of FIRRE intergenic repeating RNA element, encoded by *FIRRE* in metastasis to the lungs in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of FIRRE changed more than 85% of the human lung metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,997 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of FIRRE messenger RNA in lung metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of FIRRE during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

II. Cell culture model of lung metastatic propensity; human breast cancer.

n=2 MDA-PAR lung metastasis cancer cells (MDA-MB-231, low metastatic potential)

n=2 MDA-LM2 lung metastasis cancer cells (MDA-MB-231, high metastatic potential)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
286467	1.63E-01	0.859	-1.396071	-1.1987629	8.82	FIRRE	1840/10554	82.6

Through measurement of total transcription in cells with low metastatic potential as compared to cells with high metastatic potential using the MDA-LM2 model derived from MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells, we validated differential expression of FIRRE in metastasis to the lung in breast cancer (**Chart 2**). The expression of FIRRE here changed more than 80% of the lung metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 10,554 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating higher expression of FIRRE messenger RNA in breast cancer cells with high potential to metastasize to the lungs, demonstrating viability of FIRRE as a therapeutic target to manage disease progression and dissemination to the lungs in humans with breast cancer.

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Thus, differential and increased expression of FIRRE defines the lung metastatic transcriptome in human breast cancer.

Discussion

We provided evidence here that the DXZ4 locus-encoded non-coding RNA *FIRRE* (which controls Xist expression) is activated in the lungs in humans with breast cancer. The data allude to a broader role for Xist activation/repression dynamics in driving metastasis *in vivo*.

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Methods

We utilized GSE191230 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the lungs and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE186637, in human breast cancer cells for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and microarray data (published and public) and R-based computational methods.